

DIFFERENT OPTIMIZATION METHOD FOR SITTING AND SIZING OF DISTRIBUTED GENERATION IN ELECTRICAL NETWORK

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Abstract:

In distributed network losses are compare to transmission and generation system. Losses reduce the efficiency of system and making worst scenario for power system. Several methods are used to reduce the losses like incorporating fact devices, restructuring of power system etc. Distributed generation is now becoming popular for not only reducing the total burden on generator but also for decreasing the losses in power system. the main problems comes for siting & sizing for distribution generation so that it should be placed effectively , hence increase the total efficiency of power system network . Several methods are studied for optimal placements of distributed generation & at last comparative analysis is given.

KEYWORDS: DG (distributed generation), sitting & sizing, OVSI, MVSI

I. INTRODUCTION

With restructured environment, electric utilities are seeking new technologies to serve their customers with acceptable range of power quality and reliability. Utilities are continuously planning the expansion of their electrical networks in order to face the load growth and to properly supply their consumers. Distributed Generation (DG) sources have been popular due to their potential solution for some issues, like the deregulation in power system and improving the performance of Distribution System. The optimal placement of DG is needed for maximizing the DG benefits in power system such as improving reliability and stability.

Some economical and environmental concerns will accentuate the movement from centralized generation towards distribution generation. losses surely have important effect on the revenues of

electric power companies, green house emission and the cost of energy supplied therefore decreasing technical and non technical losses is a running test in most of distribution companies .Installing DG units in distribution system has been proposed as an effective measure to minimize losses. Due to the growing demand for electric energy, traditional T&D may work close to stability limit which will in turn expose system security to risk. In this regard, the voltage instability may cause partial and total blackouts in power system network. Hence the voltage stability limits are very important for distribution utilities whereby these limits restrict surplus load serving.

For loss minimization under ODGP all problem variables should be simultaneously optimized in order to ensure a non biased solution. Artificial intelligence optimization methods occupy a prominent place in solving the optimization problems concerning the optimal DG placement and sizing. Economic load dispatch, optimal power flow and optimal reactive power dispatch nonlinear problems are some of the most important optimization problems in power system operation and planning for allocating generation to the committed units.

Nowadays demand response has become one of the essential components of recent deregulated power system as it can offer many distinguished features such as availability, quickness and applicability. The detection of voltage collapse is essential to avoid possible voltage collapse for the preventive control actions & voltage security assessment. one effective way to know the locations where the point where voltage collapses appear in a serve contingency.

With the increasing electric power demand, power systems become stressed, resulting in undesirable voltage and frequency conditions. The connection of distributed generation (DG) to the electricity distribution networks has reformed the traditional theory of the downstream power flow and the short circuit capacity. In some occasions, DG could be connected without any complications. However, DG may also have extreme significant impact on the voltage profile and the network short circuit level, in which may limit the connection of the DG to the network. The uptake of installing DG units is to the connection of distributed generation (DG) to the electricity distribution networks has reformed there place the conventional centralized power stations that are highly dependent on fossil fuels. The advantages of connecting DG may be unloading sub transmission and transmission system, losses, improving power quality, and reliability.

Nowadays electrical power system are facing different technical economical and environmental issues. A viable way to relieve such issues is to use distributed generation (DG) units. A decentralized control method for Electronically Interfaced Distributed Generations (EI-DGs) that controls their output frequencies, power generations, voltages during grid-connected, islanding and synchronizing modes.

A load concentration factor (LCF) is introduced to select the optimal location(s) for DG placement. The integration of DG(s) becomes the most economical solution to meet the increased demand due to load growth in the conventional system. While providing environmentally friendly energy and while helping to meet the increasing load economically, DGs are also proven to be beneficial in providing reduction in power losses, improving voltage profile, and improving the power handling capability and power quality of the system.

As the electrical energy demand grows yearly, large amount of capital cost needed to install new power stations, expansion of transmission and distribution lines. The seamounts can be reduced by using distributed generators which can be conveniently located closer to load centres. Impact different penetration schemes to the optimal distributed generation placement problem for loss minimization. Electricity distribution network (DN) is the major component in the electricity system of many countries which spreads across their territories. It has the function of transmitting power directly to additional loads.

The power system reliability mainly depends on the smooth operation and continuity of supply of the distribution network. The less power interruption at the consumer side, the more reliable the distribution network. An effective method based on Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to recognize the switching operation plan for feeder reconfiguration and optimum value of DG size simultaneously.

The growing demand in the power system has posed a challenging task to power system engineers in maintaining a reliable and safe system cheaply. In the heavily loaded network, the load current drawn from the source would raise. This may lead to an increase in voltage drop and system losses. The performance of distribution system becomes inefficient due to the reduction in voltage magnitude and increase in distribution losses. Therefore, the operating cost will also increase. With this regard, changing environment of power systems design and operation have necessitated the need to consider active distribution network by incorporating Distributed Generation units (DGs) sources .The integration of DGs in distribution system would lead to

improving the voltage profile, reliability improvement such as service restoration and uninterrupted power supply and increase energy efficiency. The distribution feeder reconfiguration (DFR) is one of the mainly significant control schemes in the distribution networks which can be affected by the interconnection of DGs. Generally, the DFR is defined as varying the topological structure of distribution feeders by changing the open/closed status of sectionalisation and tie switches so that the power losses is minimized, and the constraints are met. the reconfiguration methodology was apply to the radial power system for service restoration, load balancing, and repairs of the power system.

As the INDIA addresses the challenges of achieving energy sustainability in the 21st century, the recognition of the need to find alternatives to current practices has been stymied by the identification of many complexities: including matching supply and demand, the scale of current and projected needs, and the difficulty of replacing the present unidirectional system with far more complex hybrid systems utilizing disparate sources and supplies of energy. By applying modern technology and ecological knowledge, we can utilize local resources in a way that causes little or no environmental damage. In recent time, local onsite power production was gradually abandoned in favour of ever larger and more centralized energy production. Local energy production reduces waste by lessening dependence on the infrastructure of large power plants.

II. DISTRIBUTED GENERATION

Distributed Generation can be defined as an electrical power source connected directly to the distribution network or on the consumer side of the meter. The technical benefits of DG in terms of voltage profile improvement, line loss reduction and environmental impact reduction.

DG units are defined as small scale generating units installed at distribution systems near load centres. Distributed generation is an alternative for centralized generation. The phrases “distributed generation”, “dispersed generation”, “district generation”, “decentralised generation”, “embedded generation”, “local generation” and “on site generation” are used interchangeably.

There are different definitions for DG. For instance, EPRI defines DG as “utilisation of small (0–5 MW), modular power generation technologies dispersed throughout a utility's distribution system in order to reduce T&D loading, defer the upgrade of T&D facilities, reduce losses, improve power quality and reliability”. DG units may be grid connected or work standalone the

DG's with ratings between 1 and 5 kW are called micro DG's, the DG's with ratings between 5 kW and 5 MW are called small DG's, the DG's with ratings in 5-50 MW are called medium DG's and the DG's with ratings in 50-300MW are called large DG's.

DG's can be based on renewable or non-renewable energy sources. The common technologies adopted in DG's are micro turbines, fuel cells, wind, solar, hydro and biomass units. DG units may be utility owned or customer owned.

From another perspective, DG's can be classified into four types; Type I DG's, named as P-type DG's, only generate active power and exchange no reactive power with the grid; Type II DG's, named Q-type DG's, only exchange reactive power with the grid. Type III DG's, named PQ DG's, supply active and reactive power to the grid. Eventually, type IV DG's, named $P\bar{Q}$ DG's, supply active power but absorb reactive power from grid. In power flow studies, DG's are usually modelled as negative load.

A brief introduction of some commonly used DG technologies has been provided below a detailed comparison of different DG technologies has been provided as a table. Diesel generators: The most popular DG technology is diesel generator. It is very suitable for standalone operation. It can be started and shut down almost spontaneously.

Micro turbines: They are high speed and mechanically simple devices. Natural gas and biogas are their commonly used fuels. They are dispatch able sources of energy. As a developing technology, its efficiency is continually increasing and its cost is continually decreasing. Micro-turbines are not very environment friendly, since they give out harmful emissions; however, the emissions from natural gas are lower than that of other fossil fuels.

Solar DG's: Solar photovoltaic (solar PV's) convert the energy of sunlight into direct current electricity. Through inverters, they interface with the grid. A PV system uses solar panels that are composed of solar cells. Solar PV's represent a sustainable, clean, free and abundant source of electric power. They first mass produced in year 2000. Initially, it was a very expensive technology however, its cost is continually decreasing and the efficiency of solar PV systems is continually increasing. Therefore, the penetration of PV's is quickly increasing. Its worldwide installed capacity doubles every couple of years. In 2014, worldwide installed PV capacity reached 177 GW which was around 35 times the installed PV capacity of 2006. Solar PV's along with Other renewable sources generating units play the role of a hedge against price volatility of fossil fuel based generation . The main drawback of PV's is that their output power is a function

of solar irradiation and temperature which vary constantly, therefore, their output power is not fixed at different times.

Wind power: Like solar PV's, they produce clean emission free electricity, they need small land, although they are considered visually disturbing .They tend to complement solar PV's. Days without sun tend to be windy and vice versa, therefore hybridisation of solar and wind units seems to be a good idea. Wind farms can be of two kinds; onshore wind farms and offshore wind farms. In 2014, the global installed wind capacity reached to 336 GW which means 4% of the world's installed capacity. Since the output power of wind turbines depends on the wind speed and wind speed varies over time, the output power of wind turbines is time dependent. Therefore, wind generation units similar to solar PV's suffer from intermittency of their output power.

The problem of finding optimal type, location and size of DG units in distribution systems is referred to as “DG allocation problem”.

Table1.Technologies for Distributed Generation

<i>Technology</i>	<i>Typical available size per module</i>
Wind turbine	200 Watt–3 MW
Micro-Turbines	35 kW–1 MW
Combined cycle gas T.	35–400 MW
Internal combustion engines	5 kW–10 MW
Combustion turbine	1–250 MW
Small hydro	1–100 MW
Micro hydro	25 kW–1 MW
Photovoltaic arrays	20 Watt – 100kW
Solar thermal, central receive	1-10 MW
Solar thermal, Lutz system	10–80 MW
Biomass, e.g. based on gasification	100 kW–20 MW
Fuel cells, phos acid	200 kW–2 MW
Fuel cells, molten carbonate	250 kW–2 MW
Fuel cells, proton exchange	1 kW–250 kW
Fuel cells, solid oxide	250 kW–5 MW
Geothermal	5–100 MW
Ocean energy	100 kW–1 MW
Stirling engine	2–10 Kw
Battery storage	500 kW–5 MW

Fig.3.1. Distributed Generation types and technologies

III. OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES

(1) A weighted multi objective index method

$$VI_i = \sum_{k=1}^{nbus} (1 - V_k)^2$$

$$WMOVI = (\omega_1 * CNVI) + (\omega_2 * TNVI)$$

(2) Imperialistic competitive algorithm method

$$I(m) = \frac{v(s)\delta(s) - v(m)\delta(m)}{r(m) + jx(m)}$$

$$r(m) = \text{real} \left[\frac{v(m)\delta(m) - v(s)\delta(s)}{I(m)} \right]$$

$$x(m) = \text{imag} \left[\frac{v(m)\delta(m) - v(s)\delta(s)}{I(m)} \right]$$

$$OVSI = \sum_{m=2}^{NB} VSI(m)$$

(3) Distributed cooperative control method

$$x_i = f_i[x_i] + g_i[x_i]u_i$$

$$y_i = h_i(x_i)$$

$$\dot{u} = -Lu + \beta v$$

$$u = [u_i]^T$$

$$L = [l_{ij}]$$

$$L = \begin{cases} -1 & j \in N_i \\ |N_i| & j = 1 \end{cases}$$

(4) Load concentration factor based analytical method

$$Q_{DGi} = aP_{DGi}$$

$$a = (\text{sign}) \tan(\cos^{-1} PF_{DG})$$

$$P_i = P_{DGi} - P_{Di}$$

$$Q_i = Q_{DGi} - Q_{Di} = aP_{DGi} - Q_{Di}$$

$$P_l = \sum_{i,j=1}^n [\alpha_{ij} \{(P_{DGi} - P_{Di})P_j + (aP_{DGi} - Q_{Di})Q_j\} + \beta_{ij} \{(aP_{DGi} - Q_{Di})P_j - (P_{DGi} - P_{Di})Q_j\}]$$

$$\frac{\partial P_L}{\partial P_{DGi}} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^n [\alpha_{ij} (P_j + aQ_j) + \beta_{ij} (aP_j - Q_j)] = 0$$

$$L_{CFi} = \sum_{j \in C_i} P_{Di}$$

(5) GA method

$$\text{Min } P_{Losses} = f(x)$$

$$\text{Min } P_{Losses}(P_{DG}) = R * \left(\frac{D * A * P}{\beta} \right)^2$$

(6) PSO Algorithm

$$N_{\beta i} = \{X_{i-r}, X_{i-r+1}, X_{i-1}, \dots \dots \dots X_{i+r}\}$$

$$V_{ij(t+1)} = wV_{ij}(t) + C_1R_1(P_{ij}(t) - X_{ij}(t)) + C_2R_2(P_{gi}(t) - X_{ij}(t))$$

$$X_{ij}(t+1) = X_{ij}(t) + V_{ij}(t+1)$$

$$w(t) = w_{up} - (w_{up} - w_{low}) \frac{t}{T_{max}}$$

(7) Probabilistic approach

$$T_{up} = -MTTF \times \ln U$$

$$T_{repair} = -MTTR \times \ln U'$$

$$ENS = \frac{1}{N_y} \sum_{t=1}^{8760N_y} \sum_{i=1}^N P_{SHi,t} \times P_{Di,t}$$

$$COST = \frac{1}{N_y} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{\forall d} \sum_{t=1}^N P_{SHi,t} \times P_{Di,t}$$

(8) UPSO method

$$GV_i(t+1) = X[V_i(t) + C_1 R_1(P_i(t) - X_i(t)) + C_2 R_2(P_g(t) - X_i(t))]$$

$$LV_i(t+1) = X[V_i(t) + C_1 R_1(P_i(t) - X_i(t)) + C_2 R_2(P_l(t) - X_i(t))]$$

$$U \leq 0.5$$

$$V_i(t+1) = U R_3 GV_i(t+1) + (1 - \mu) LV_i(t+1)$$

$$U > 0.5$$

$$V_i(t+1) = U GV_i(t+1) + (1 - \mu) R_3 LV_i(t+1)$$

(9) DN reconfiguration method

$$g(x) = \begin{cases} |U_i|^2 G_{ii} + \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n |\dot{U}_i \dot{U}_n \dot{Y}_{ik}| \cos(\theta_{ik} + \delta_k - \delta_i) - P_{DGi} + P_{tai-i} = 0 \\ -|\dot{U}|^2 \beta_{ii} + \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^n |\dot{U}_i \dot{U}_n \dot{Y}_{ik}| \sin(\theta_{ik} + \delta_k - \delta_i) - Q_{Dgi} + Q_{tai-i} = 0 \end{cases}$$

(10) Butterfly particle swarm optimization method

$$s(t) = \exp - \left(\frac{Maxit - iter}{Maxit} \right)$$

$$p(t) = \frac{F_{gbest}}{\sum(F_{lbest} + F_{gbest})}$$

F_{gbest} = Fitness of global best solution

F_{lbest} = Fitness of local best solution

$$A_1 K_1 = A_2 K_2$$

$$A_2 = 0.9 A_1$$

$$\frac{K_1}{K_2} = 0.9 \text{ \& } K_1 < K_2$$

$$C_1 + C_2 = 4$$

$$A_2 = (4 - A_1)(0.9)$$

$$A_1 + A_2 < 4$$

$$A_1 \& A_2 < 2$$

$$C_1 = \left(\left(\frac{2}{3} - 2 \right) * \left(\frac{iter}{maxit} \right) \right) + 2$$

$$C_2 = 2 * \left(\frac{iter}{maxit} \right)$$

$$\emptyset = C_1 + C_2$$

$$C_{eq} = \frac{2.0}{2.0} - \emptyset - S_{qrt} (\emptyset^2 - 4 * \emptyset)$$

$$\omega(t) = 0.2 + \left(\frac{maxit - iter}{maxit} \right)$$

$$v(i + 1) = C_{eq} * (\omega(i) * v(i))$$

IV. PROBLEM FORMATION OF DG

$$P_{Load} + P_{Losses} - \sum P_i = 0$$

$$VSI(m) \geq 0$$

$$f = \min(P_L)$$

V. INDICES

In this work several indices will be computed in order to describe the effect of load models due to the presence of DG. These indices are defined as follows:

(1) Real and Reactive Power Loss Indices (ILP and ILQ): The real and reactive power loss indices are defined as

$$ILP = \frac{[P_{LDG}]}{[P_L]}$$
$$ILQ = \frac{[Q_{LDG}]}{[Q_L]}$$

where P_{LDG} and Q_{LDG} are the real and reactive power losses of the distribution system after inclusion of DG. P_L and Q_L are the real and reactive system losses without DG in the distribution system.

2) *Voltage Profile Index* (IVD): One of the advantages of proper location and size of the DG is the improvement in voltage profile. This index penalizes the size/location pair which gives higher voltage deviations from the nominal value (V_{nom}). In this way, closer the index to zero better is the network performance. The *IVD* can be defined as

$$IVD = \sum_{i=2}^n \left[\frac{|\bar{V}_{NOM}| - |\bar{V}_i|}{|\bar{V}_{NOM}|} \right]$$

Where n is the number of buses. Normally, the voltage limits ($V_{min} \leq V_i \leq V_{max}$) at a particular bus is taken as technical constraint, and thus the value of the *IVD* is normally small and within the permissible limits.

Table 2 Load types and exponent values

$$P = P_0(V)^\alpha$$

$$Q = Q_0(V)^\beta$$

Load	α	β
Constant	0	0
Industrial Load	0.18	6
Residential Load	0.92	4.04
Commercial Load	1.51	3.4

(3) MVA Capacity Index(IC): As a consequence of supplying power near to loads ,MVA flows may diminish in some sections of the network, thus releasing more capacity, but in other sections they may also increase to levels beyond distribution line limits (if line limits are not taken as constraints). The index (IC) gives important information about the level of MVA flow/currents through the network regarding the maximum capacity of conductors. This gives the information about need of system line upgrades. Values higher than unity (calculated MVA flow values higher than the MVA capacity) of the index given the amount of capacity violation in term of line flow whereas the lower values indicated the capacity available.

$$IC = \sum_{i=1}^{NOLmax} \left(\frac{|\bar{S}_i|}{|CS_i|} \right)$$

Where *NOL* is the number of lines, *S_i* is the MVA flow in line *i* and *CS_i* is the MVA capacity of line *i* . The benefit of placing DG in a system in context of line capacity released is measured by finding the difference in *IC* between system with and without DG. The avoidance of flow near to the flow limits is an important criterion as it indicates that how earlier the system need to be upgraded and thus adding to the cost. Normally, the limits ($S_i \leq S_{i, max}$) at a particular line is taken as a strict constraint .

4) Short Circuit Level Index (ISC): This index is related to the protection and sensitivity issues since it evaluates the short circuit current at each bus with and without DG .

$$ISC = \frac{I_{SC\text{ without DG}} - I_{SC\text{ with DG}}}{I_{SC\text{ without DG}}}$$

Where *without DGSC I* is the short circuit current before installing the DG and *with DGSC I* is the short circuit current after installing the DG.

VI. CONCLUSION

Several methods are presented to optimal location of distributed generation according to loss function with their mathematical modeling. Stochastic & deterministic types of methods is available to DG siting & sizing .stochastic methods like UPSO, BPSO have higher accuracy & sensitivity compare to deterministic methods ,but randomness is more . Several indices could also be identity to check the system parameters like short circuit current capacity, MVA capacity etc.

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